

Milestone Report M15

Key selected interoperability challenge demonstrations implemented

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Table of contents

Introduction	3
Sensitive Data Transfer Between Trusted Research Environments (TREs)	3
Reusability of Information from Secure Environments	4
Technical Infrastructure and Tools	4
Conclusion	5
Technical Challenges	5
Governance Challenges	5
Legal and Policy Challenges	5

Introduction

This milestone report outlines the key findings and outcomes from the interoperability challenge demonstrations selected during the first Requirements and Capabilities workshop (RC1) in May 2024¹. The focus in this report is on two critical validators that are implemented:

1. Sensitive Data Transfer Between Trusted Research Environments (TREs)
2. Creation of Reusable Information from Secure Environments. This includes the development of reusable datasets aimed at bridging gaps in the research data life cycle.

These areas of focus are particularly relevant to interoperability requirement categories 1, and 4, which encompass data transfer between environments, and data lifecycle management, respectively. For further details, please refer to [Section 7.2.2](#)² of Deliverable D13.1 report.

The “1st EOSC-ENTRUST Evaluation & Adoption Workshop”³, held in Helsinki on September 24-25, 2024, served as a platform for [showcasing](#) these validators.

Sensitive Data Transfer Between Trusted Research Environments (TREs)

The primary demonstration was centered on the transfer of sensitive data between two TREs: SAFE (University of Bergen), as TRE A and TSD (University of Oslo), as TRE B. In this scenario, TRE A functions as the client, initiating data export processes, while TRE B serves as the server, responsible for managing incoming data.

To facilitate file import and export, including JSON data handling, a File API was utilised. TSD has developed and released an open source API command-line client for file transfers, available at <https://pypi.org/project/tsd-api-client/3.5.3/>

The demonstration highlighted several significant challenges in the implementation of secure data transfer between TREs. A primary concern was the need to respect the distinct policies and regulations of each TRE during data exchanges. These policies play a crucial role in defining the parameters of data sharing, and the authorized recipients.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/11278853>

² <https://zenodo.org/records/12703951>

³ <https://zenodo.org/records/13860340>

Another notable challenge encountered was the management of logging requirements without reliance on centralized infrastructure. Both TRE A and TRE B necessitated secure and verifiable logging of all data transfer-related activities. This decentralized approach to logging is essential for maintaining the integrity and traceability of data transfers between independent TREs.

Reusability of Information from Secure Environments

An aspect of the interoperability demonstration was the emphasis on reusing information from secure environments. It highlighted processes that facilitate the sharing and reuse of data for research purposes, making sensitive datasets accessible to approved users without compromising their security. The demonstration showcased tools, such as the Clinical Research Data Sharing Repository⁴, which allow users to search for, request, and access secure datasets.

The system architecture demonstrated a layered repository storage structure that organizes data hierarchically under specific studies, datasets, and instances, allowing for efficient data management. The demonstration also introduced several components, including the Repository Manager, Data Object Provider, and TSD User, which together facilitate the flow of data while maintaining the requisite checks for data integrity and policy adherence.

Technical Infrastructure and Tools

The demonstration involved several technical tools that support data sharing and interoperability. Key among these were the TSD API Client and the ECRIN metadata schemas. The ECRIN metadata schemas⁵, on the other hand, provide standardized ways to describe datasets, facilitating easier discovery and consistent data management across different environments.

Additionally, the ECRIN RMS user interface and backend services were presented, providing a comprehensive platform for managing data requests and ensuring that sensitive data transfers comply with research regulations and repository-specific policies. These services were aimed at making the data sharing process more efficient while ensuring compliance with data governance standards.

The data management component was presented as a core aspect of interoperability. It features a repository structure organized under a hierarchy that follows the pattern:

⁴ <https://crr.gitbook.io/crdsr>

⁵ <https://github.com/ecrin-github/esbs-django>

repository > study > dataset > data instance. Each data instance has specific permissions, managed through group identifiers such as "pnnn-r<dataset>-group" and "pnnn-w<dataset>-group" to distinguish between read and write access.

Conclusion

The demonstration of safe data transfer between TREs and access to reusable information from a secure environment has highlighted significant progress. However, several challenges remain that require further attention. These challenges can be categorized into technical, governance, and legal aspects:

Technical Challenges

- Implementation of a logging system that allows access to logs for transfer of data between involved TREs
- Ensuring secure user authentication and authorization across multiple TREs

Governance Challenges

- Creating a comprehensive governance framework that allows for effective auditing of data access and usage.
- Implementing the Five Safes framework (Safe People, Safe Projects, Safe Settings, Safe Data, and Safe Outputs) in the context of inter-TRE data sharing.

Legal and Policy Challenges

- Developing legal agreements that facilitate data sharing while respecting the policies of all involved TREs.
- Harmonizing access policies across different TREs to enable seamless yet secure data exchange.